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BRINGING INDUSTRY AUTHENTICITY TO TRADITIONAL TAUGHT PROGRAMME ELEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses a project which leverages professional contacts to build industry linked activities into areas of the curriculum which are often seen as focussed more on fundamental theory and less on the wider aspects of practical implementation.

While part of a much wider initiative, to show the process, we will focus in on one exemplar - the development of a learning package in support of pump flow - classic fluid dynamics, taught normally through theory classes supported by laboratory exercises. The new development however involved collaboration with a major supplier of fluid handling equipment with whom we had existing contact via recent alumni. The result was an online self-directed learning package combining a compact masterclass with a senior engineer together with a 'have a go yourself' active and adaptive mixed-media activity with a recent graduate acting as host. The paper reports on this experience, reflections from academic, industrial and student partners and offers a guide to those wishing to try something similar particularly in current Covid restricted times when physical involvement with industry is otherwise difficult.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Industry involvement in degrees

Involvement of industry in engineering degrees is seen as vital to add currency and authenticity to the learning experience [1]. This involvement may take the form of both direct engagement with the learning experience via student facing activities or indirect engagement such as industrial advisory or steering boards [2] designed to support the teaching team in their development of curriculum.

1.2 Typical touch points and engagement mechanisms

Direct industrial input into the curriculum commonly involves engagement in dissertations, capstone exercise [3], visits [4], guest lectures [5,6], internships [7,8] or design projects [9,10]. These typically are linked to design type modules [11,12] or projects and are often biased toward later years at which point students are perceived to have accrued the skills needed to cope with the challenges posed.

1.3 Engagement in taught aspects of the programme

Less common is the embedding of industrially linked activity in conventional didactic topics such as core underpinning engineering science particularly in early years. Normally taught via lectures, tutorials and laboratory exercises, these core skills modules impart the requisite theoretical technical knowledge but may offer less in building the confidence students need to allow them to use this theory in real world scenarios. A student on a fluid dynamics course may be able to specify an idealised pump for a job based on calculations of pressures and flow capacities but may not join this up with practical considerations such as servicing, cost, spares retention, over or undersizing to deal with uncertainties in the expected demand, performance drop-off over time etc. This potentially creates a confidence and skills gap for graduates transitioning to industry.

1.4 Industry club

To aid in engagement with industry a number of institutions around the world have developed industry clubs [13,14]. For the industrial companies, such a scheme offers a low risk, low cost involvement with the University, access to students to undertake projects and helps raise awareness in the students minds of companies and sectors which may not have the profile of more obvious areas of the graduate jobs market. At Aston University such clubs have been running for three or so years in Mechanical Engineering, Chemical Engineering and Computer Science. Initially these focussed on placing industrially linked projects with final year dissertation students but the scope has gradually increased to look at other opportunities to share activity. This paper looks at how the partnership has been expanded into the taught elements of the programme with a particular consideration of implementation under Covid restrictions which has made company visits, face to face guest talks and similar activities difficult.

1.5 Proposal

To address the lack of industrial content in didactic engineering science modules it was proposed that a number of interactive online case studies be developed to help show how fundamental engineering science can be applied in authentic industrial problems. A small team consisting of an academic, a material developer and a member of the University business link unit was assembled.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Raising awareness

As with many initiatives of this type, raising awareness among industrial and academic partners of the opportunities is a key first step (Fig.1). To achieve this and with Covid restrictions limiting direct interaction, an online event was held to which all academics and industry club members were invited. Here a number of students working on industry club linked projects presented their work. In addition, pilot work on the design of the interactive case studies was presented.

Fig. 1. Educational material development process

2.2 Identification of partners

With awareness raised, a number of academics came forward with areas they felt could benefit from added industrial authenticity. In some cases, they already had industrial partners in mind but were needing support in getting over the inertia to make development of support material viable. In other cases academics would approach the team with a need and the supporting team would then help them map these needs to the strengths of partners within the Industry Club or wider industrial contacts with the required skills who may then be able to work with them.

2.3 Topic development

With partners and academics identified, a meeting was set up to clarify objectives and ensure a consensus between all those involved in terms of commitment and hoped for outcomes.

This was then followed by specific meetings between the developer, academics and industrial representatives before beginning material development.

3 DEVELOPMENT OF MATERIAL IN VIRTUAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

3.1 The Context

The work was carried out under fluctuating national lockdown conditions imposed to control Covid-19. This precluded visits by academics or the development team to the

industrial partners or vice-versa. While this prevented direct contact between students and the industrial partners it did encourage the development of virtual and online material to support the learning which then has the capacity to be reused for other cohorts without significant extra workload.

3.2 The Virtual Learning Environment

While virtual learning environments (VLE) have been around for a couple of decades the impact of Covid-19 have seen these move to a leading rather than supporting role in the learning process.

To provide a readily accessible development environment for both the development team and the students the standard VLE available at Aston University, “Blackboard”, was utilised. As with most VLEs this offers the opportunity to deposit documents and videos for students to view while also offering interactive features such as quizzes, tests and adaptive release of material based on completion of previous tasks.

3.3 Material Development

While the development team was open to delivering a tailored learning package to suit each case, the example presented here (Fig.2) covers the development of a response to an authentic query sent to a water services supply company. The query was made in relation to changes in the existing industrial set up to introduce variation and to establish if such variation was within the performance of the water pump already installed. The educational material developed was to be suitable for use in a second year fluid dynamics module with the module leader a key part of the development team.

The material developed was designed to augment and follow on from the normal delivery of academic theory supported by simple case studies, tutorial problem solving and laboratory exercises. The newly developed material was then to complement these underpinnings with an online package of interactive material to contextualise the theory in an authentic setting. This learning reinforcement comes from the fact that students must first analyse the brief given in the query, make sense of it and define what needs to be calculated themselves with the workflow moving from the brief to the solution

To make the material interactive, significant use was made of relevant VLE tools. Videos were used to introduce the company and the role of the lead engineer, a former graduate. This progressed to a video run through of a typical scenario when the company is asked to devise a pumping solution for a customer. At points through this process, small check quizzes were used to allow students to check their understanding and adaptive release allowed material to only be released to students on completion of previous steps.

The material was based on the successful talks carried out online between the educational developer and the industrial engineer. There were a number of consultations between the developer and the module lead academic to ensure the

Fig. 2. Structure of Online Industry Linked Learning Material for Pump Problem

level of sophistication and difficulty was set at the right level for the group of students. This verification also allowed for consistency in wording used between the material delivered as a part of the course and the one developed in partnership with the industry. There has been circumstantial evidence from the students that they experience fatigue from excessive use of computer for studies. As a result, the introductory parts were trimmed to represent relevant topics and grouped as 'non-obligatory but beneficial', giving a student a choice to engage with the material if desired to do so.

The tasks themselves were designed to ease the students into the activity beginning by setting out the task, explaining and providing necessary information. The students were then asked a true/false question on the brief to test the ability to turn a real-life scenario into appropriate engineering task themselves – a key skill that had been noted as not fully explored in the current delivery of curriculum. New recording material was then released upon the answer to either view the summary for the students to confirm if their analysis concurs with that of a senior engineer and if not to view the process taken to conduct it.

The framework created was also enhanced by a 'how to video' delivered by the educational material developer showing how to navigate through the module and use various aspects of it.

3.4 Test and Refine

As part of the creation process, the learning material devised was partly co-developed and tested by students prior to full deployment. Key elements to refine at this stage by the team including student input include:

- Technical accuracy
- Industrial authenticity
- Clarity of material
- Validity of any tests
- Usability and robustness of online module

The approach taken by student participants in trials varied between them, however, most typically participants would take breaks at the point when new content was unlocked. Lack of certainty over how much time to commit to the task was a challenging aspect for the students. The input required was individual and varied from participant to participant subject to the level of engagement. It was possible to breeze through the material without much commitment just as it was possible to spend a few hours completing the tasks. Student feedback was collected as an interview following engagement with the material. There was some agreement between the participants in the areas such as

Participants raised the issue of technical difficulty that the task created. Although some of the students taking part in testing were not on the 2nd year Mechanical

Engineering course but on other engineering courses. This posed a challenge to assess if the students will be able to complete the 'brief analysis' independently.

Students were very surprised by the specialist terminology used in the material presented, which showed the importance of introducing the external presenters into the modules to offer exposure to these terms.. The online delivery offered the students an opportunity to pause video to search for unknown words and return to it when completed. The vocabulary was specific to water industry and therefore might have caused uncertainty compared to more general one used in the module delivery.

The material was described as clear and easy to follow, however, some participants raised an issue regarding the quality of the recording. This might have been caused by internet bandwidth issues at the student end but as the material was recorded in two separate sessions some inconsistencies between the video were noted such as change to background noise or the size of the font.

The test was limited to self-reporting by the students as to whether the brief and the problem analysis was completed successfully. Each phase of the activity was followed by guidance on which video to watch next. Participants did not report any issues in relation to completing the test or following the advice.

The content of the material was deemed complicated but not above the knowledge delivered in the part of the course. Accuracy of the material was felt to be very relevant to the work.

Participant were very excited about the gamification aspect of the material developed which incentivise progress. Some suggested further development of the concept to improve the interface of the module and to make it more interactive.

4 REFLECTIONS AND CONCLUSION

4.1 Reflections

By creating online content as a series of bite sized linked activities, natural breaks are created which not only aids the learning by affording break and reflection but also reflects the experience in industry.

Often in commercial work a system engineer handles multiple projects simultaneously and while progressing through the workflow, gathers information from stakeholders and while awaiting their response shifting focus elsewhere. The same is possible in this approach, where a task can be paused to ask for further information from the internal (or external) client with the response provided by the lecturer or automatically by the VLE after certain period of time. An increase in sophistication of the delivery of the material would also remove one of the drawbacks reported by the students, that is to make videos shorter and smaller tasks to make them more manageable.

It was important not to overcomplicate the questions set to the students, at times a simple 'yes/no' questions as to whether they are able to complete the task at

hand was enough to guide a student to next video for the appropriate level. It was also important to introduce an ability for the students to check their answers and to be able to watch any analysis that they might have got wrong in their own attempt, this serves a purpose of bringing the whole cohort to the same level before a new task is introduced.

4.2 Conclusions

The work presented offers a route to embedding authentic industrial content in some of the more academic areas of the teaching curriculum. The exploitation of VLE tools can enable a blended team of academics, industrialists, students and material developers to develop an online learning experience bridging some of the gaps between traditional underpinning academic theory and industrial practice. While the general approach could also be adapted to face to face activity by having the material as an online activity it helps to ensure a degree of industry contact under Covid restricted times. The development of an online package also allows the ability to access material as and when required in future and makes it easier for students to reflect and repeat until confidence is established.

There are however some issues to be aware of. Development of this material takes effort and engagement by academics, industrialists and students on an ongoing basis during the creation process. The use of a specialist developer to help smooth and act as a catalyst has helped but this may not always be available. In addition, while VLE tools are developing and becoming more sophisticated, some of the more advanced features which might have been developed to allow for example a branching rather than purely linear structure were not possible at this stage.

Despite these issues, the development has been positive and has shown a way to invigorate many traditional underpinning core engineering topics.

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